

Newspaper Usage and Preference by Undergraduates of Renaissance University Ugbawka, Enugu State.

Okoroafor C. K.

University of Agriculture and Environmental Science Library Umuagwo, Imo State.

Corresponding author: kingsley.okoroafor@uaes.edu.ng

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Abstract: Newspapers usages and preferences among undergraduates of Renaissance University Ugbawka, Enugu Nigeria has been examined. The study adopted descriptive survey design and data was collected from respondents through the administration of a closed ended questionnaire. 106 copies of questionnaire were distributed to randomly selected undergraduates from 100 to 500 levels. 104 completed and returned questionnaires were found valid for analysis. Frequencies and percentages were used for data analysis. Results from the study revealed that 51(49%) preferred electronic newspapers, 31(29.8%) preferred print newspapers while interestingly, 22(21.2%) preferred both print and electronic newspapers. However, the study established that respondents had different reasons for a certain format of newspaper which includes; quality of information, ease of access of a given newspaper and timely information among others. In addition, respondent's use of newspaper was mainly to update their knowledge and to keep informed on daily activities such as politics, sports and entertainment news. It was recommended that the university library should make the library web pages more visible so that users can access electronic newspaper and other e-resources with ease. They should also purchase few copies of print newspaper that would complement the electronic once.

Keywords: *Newspapers, Print, Electronic, Format, Undergraduates.*

Introduction

Newspaper is a type of media channel that plays a significant role in disseminating information on current issues. Newspapers irrespective of its kind (print or electronic) updates us; coach us and persuade us to

figure out significant issues in our various disciplines. Onwubiko (2018) asserted that newspapers have always been regarded as one of the media that ensures adequate transmission of government policies (as cited in Ufuoma (2019) Newspapers are serial publications usually printed on

newsprint and issued daily, on certain days of the week, or weekly, containing news, editorial comment, regular columns, letters to the editor, cartoon, advertising, and other items of current information. A newspaper can also be said to be as publication issued in periodically or in a successive parts containing the most recent news. Anaeto (2019) asserted that newspapers carry pertinent information on recent event that are eye-catching to readers; its main function is educating, informing and entertaining the general public, but some private newspapers contain information that are not dependable and therefore not factaul or useful to the young ones. However, the quest to read newspapers can also be a function of the type students preferred. Newspapers can be in the print or electronic form. The print form is in leaves of papers usually played in the serial sections of the library, while the electronic form of newspapers are accessed electronically with the aid of computer devices. By carrying out a survey-based empirical study focusing on newspaper usages and preferences among undergraduates. This paper aims at examining and providing significant information and awareness which would in turn aid us make available preferred newspaper for maximum usage and satisfaction.

Study Area/Case study

Renaissance University Ugbawka (RNU) in Enugu State Nigeria was established and approved by the Federal Executive Council in 2005 and admitted its first set of undergraduates in 2007. The University Library houses information resources both print and non-print form. The university was established under the Federal Government of Nigeria initiative to raise, build and shape human capital. Renaissance University library is the heart of academic activities of the institution. The university community make use of the library for teaching, learning, and research and for total development. Renaissance university library run shift duties in order to ensure that users make good use of the materials available. The library has capacity to accommodate large number of students and also it has various departmental libraries servicing the students and lecturers.

Statement of the problem

Newspapers are serial publications that appear in successive parts and intended to be continued indefinitely. Newspapers be it in print or electronic form, keep students and researchers informed of current trends in their various research areas. in some cases newspapers carry information that may take decades before they are seen in books, and at times, they may not appear at

all. Obviously, researchers have carried out study on the importance of print and electronic newspapers media in libraries, yet user's utilization of newspaper media(print and electronic) in Renaissance University library irrespective of the form seems to have been unexplored and unexamined. This study deems it necessary to investigate the present state of newspaper usage and preference by undergraduates of Renaissance University in order to unravel the extent of use, preferred format and the militating factors confronting users in the use of newspaper in Renaissance university library

Purpose of the Study

The researcher's main objective is to investigate the usage and preference of newspapers by undergraduates of Renaissance University

1. To investigate the extent of Newspapers usage in Renaissance University library
2. TO examine the form of newspapers preferred by students of Renaissance university.
3. To Investigate the Purpose of newspapers usage in the library
4. To ascertain the challenges encountered in the use of print newspapers in the University library

5. To ascertain the challenges encountered in the use of Electronic newspapers in the University library

Research Questions

1. To what extent do students use Newspapers in the University Library?
2. What form of newspaper is preferred by students of Renaissance University?
3. What Purposes do students use newspapers in the library?
4. What are the challenges encountered in the use of print newspapers in the library?
5. What are the challenges encountered in the use of Electronic newspapers in the library?

Literature Review

There are numerous studies on the usage and preference of newspapers among readers but only few have a direct focus on students' usage and preference (Hassan and Latiff, 2018; FouziaNaz, 2015). Kobusingye (2016) in a study aimed at evaluating readers' access and use of newspapers at Makerere University library, findings affirmed different reasons of readers' preference for a certain newspaper and version. Results revealed that majority (62%) preferred printed newspapers as compared to (38%) that preferred online newspapers.

Oluwadamilola (2020) carried out a similar research on survey of newspaper usage and preference by undergraduates of Obafemi Awolowo. The result of the findings also reveals that majority (28.6%) students of the said University preferred print newspaper to electronics (21.4%). Reasons for the preference of the print version was stated to be easy access, some details missing online and not affected by technological problems and so on. Further, reasons for preference of online newspaper by readers was said to include; simultaneous and multiple access, use of key words to search for the articles, easy reference to other related articles and as well as instant public opinion.

Similarly, Eze (2022) in a study on newspaper reading habits among students of Imo State, Nigeria. Findings of the study shows that majority (64%) read newspaper in electronic form while (36%) read print version of newspaper. Reason for the high turnout on electronic version of newspaper was that the internet is more convenience to use for readers.

Okoroafor (2019) in a survey on the extent of utilization of electronic newspapers among the students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University and University of Nigeria Nsukka, Nigeria, found that 76% of the students prefer to read electronic newspaper on their mobile phone and laptops, while

52% of the students read both the print and electronic newspapers.

Further, a survey of online newspaper readers in USA revealed that majority of the online readers (90%) read the electronic newspapers despite the availability of print at their reach. It was further gathered that online newspapers have not much affected the circulation of print newspapers (Tewari, 2016).

Hassan and Azmi (2018) in a study aimed at evaluating readers preference for online newspaper in Northwestern Nigeria, found that majority of the readers (mean = 3.49) had preference for online newspapers. This is because they have access to free online versions of the print newspapers. It was further reported that majority of the readers (mean = 3.37) will continue to read the print version despite the availability of its free online counterpart.

Ashong and Henry (2017) in a survey on content preference among online and hard copy newspaper readers in Imo State, reported that 80% of readers read both version of newspapers and that 76% reported content is immaterial as a determinant of preferred version.

However, majority of literature consulted, affirmed that electronic newspapers is widely read and consulted despite the availability of print form in libraries.

Electronic newspapers, due to its convenience and ease of access especially among young readers who spend most of their time on android phones, personal computers and cheap or free internet access read electronic version of newspaper. Therefore, the relevance of electronic newspapers in institutions of higher learning is undisputed, and as a result, there is need for Nigerian academic libraries to embrace technology

Population of the study

Sani (2016) defines population as asset of all element, objects or events that are of interest in a particular study. The target (Population of this study comprises of randomly selected (106) students that uses the library.

Sampling Technique and sample size

In the study, the only respondent considered were the randomly selected students.

According to Muhammad (2012), sample size can be determined non-statically by using a face value evaluation. Sample size of the randomly selected students (106) are not to many, and as a result were used as the sample for the study

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was used for the study. Closed ended questionnaires were administered to the respondents so as to elicit information from them. Valid data was gotten from their responses and used for the analysis. The population of the study consists of undergraduates which were randomly selected, based on their physical presence/attendance in the library at the newspapers desk. 104 copies of questionnaires were returned and found valid for analysis, thereby giving a response rate of 98%. Frequencies and percentages were used for data analysis.

Table 1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

Variable	Measurement	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	45	42.5
	Female	61	57.5
Total			
Age	15-18	29	27.4
	19-22	40	37.7
	22-25	37	34.9
	25 and above	0	0
Total		100	100
Level of Study	100	12	11.3
	200	24	22.6
	300	32	30.2
	400	25	23.6
	500	13	12.3
Total		106	100

The demography reveals that all the levels of students in Renaissance university were selected for the study and they are a total of

106 students. 100 level (12-11.3%), 200 level (24-22.6%), 300 level (32-30.2%), 400 level (25-23.5%) and 500 level (13-12.2%).

Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Table 2 shows a high patronage on daily basis 51(49%), 27(26%) indicated once a week, 15(14.4%) used it twice a week, 11(10.6%). Majority of the students use newspapers daily. This findings is in agreement with the research of

Oluwadamila (2020) which reported that majority of the students read/consult newspapers on daily basis. The findings is in variation with Tewari(2016) who asserted that majority of the students consult newspaper once a week.

Table 2 Frequency of newspapers usage in the Library

S/N	Respondent	Daily	Once a week	Twice a week	Thrice a week
1	104	51(49%)	27(26%)	15(14.4%)	11(10.6%)

Table 3 established the preferred format of newspapers. The result showed that majority 51(49%) of the respondents preferred reading electronic newspapers while 31(29.8%) preferred to read print newspapers. Interestingly, 22 (21.2%) of the total population reported they read both

print and online newspapers. This finding is in variance with the research of Oluwadamila (2020), but in agreement with Eze (2022) and Okoroafor (2019) which reported majority of the respondents' preferred online/electronic newspapers to print.

Table 3 Preferred Format of Newspaper

S/N	Items	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Electronic Newspaper	51	49%
2	Print Newspaper	31	29.8%
3	Both print and Electronic	22	21.2%

Table 4 shows that majority of the respondents 79 (75.9%) read Newspapers to update their knowledge, 91(87.5) read for current affairs (politics, sports etc.), 67(64.4%) read newspaper to increase their academic performance, while 72(69.2) read

newspaper for entertainment. This findings reveals that students read newspapers more for current affairs (politic, sport etc.) and for entertainment. This findings is in agreement with Oluwadimala (2020) and Ikenwa (2020).

Table 4 Purpose of Reading Newspapers

S/N	Items	Agree	%	Disagree	%
1.	For updating knowledge	79	75.9	25	24.1
2.	For current affairs (politics, sports, etc).	91	87.5	13	12.5
3.	For education/academic purpose	67	64.4	37	35.5
4.	For entertainment	72	69.2	32	30.8

Table 5 revealed that the major challenge hindering the use of print newspapers was reported to be limited number of copies 89(85.6), 63(60.6%) also agreed to access restriction to reference section of the library, the student prefer to take newspapers to any corner of library to read and digest the

information needed without any distraction, while 74(71.2) disagreed to library staff are not willing to render service/help. 70(67.4%) disagreed to “small reading space”. This implies that the library reading spaces is adequate and that the staff is diligent and willing to render service at any point in time.

Table 5 Challenges of using print newspapers

S/N	Items	Agree	%	Disagree	%
1.	Limited number of copies	89	85.6	15	14.4
2.	Access restricted to reference section of the library	63	60.6	41	39.4
3.	Library staff are not willing to render service/help	30	28.8	74	71.2
4.	Small reading space	34	32.6	70	67.4

Table 6 showed that 78(75%) disagreed to “unstable/slow internet connectivity in the library as the major obstacle in accessing

online newspapers. 54(59.1%) disagreed limited access to computers, 58(55.7%) agreed that online news was not

comprehensive enough (limited to breaking news and headlines) while 29(27.9%) disagreed to lack of computer/internet

literacy. This implies that undergraduates of Renaissance University are not highly skilled in the use of computers.

Table 6 Challenges of using Online/electronic Newspapers

S/N	Items	Agree	%	Disagree	%
1.	Limited access to computers	50	48.9	54	59.1
2.	Unstable/slow internet	26	25	78	75
3.	Limited information (breaking news/just the headline)	58	55.7	46	44.3
4.	Lack of computer/internet literacy	75	72.1	29	27.9

Conclusion

Newspapers are essential source of information for students, lecturers, and researchers in any institution of higher learning. It is evident from the findings that electronic newspaper will continue to thrive more especially in this digital era despite its print version because of its comprehensive and detailed information which print version do not give at times. It was observed that newspapers are mostly consulted by male students; this was as a result of their additional information needs such as sporting news, current affairs and politics. In addition, the findings revealed that both format (print and electronic) newspapers are read and used by Renaissance university undergraduates in order to be vast in their field of study and as well to keep informed with global issues.

Finally, it is important that libraries continue to acquire, organize and preserve electronic newspapers as it has distinct values and is being consulted on regular basis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The library should make its web page more visible as a means of providing a guide to the use of its resources especially the electronic newspapers. internet services should be improved as well as providing computer services specifically for newspapers users.
2. The library management should purchase few copies of print in order to compliment the electronic ones.
3. The library should work on making the library reading space and its environment more conducive for studying, learning and research. This

would in turn improve readership and use of library materials.

4. The library should create awareness on the availability of both the print and electronic resources at a particular time.
5. The library should ensure that print newspapers are adequately preserved in order to prevent dust and dampness which are enemies to print materials.

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